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Examining the Relationships among Internet Addiction Procrastination Social Support and Anxiety Sensitivity*

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Abstract

In this study, it was aimed to examine the relationships between individuals' levels of internet addiction, procrastination, perceived social support and anxiety sensitivity levels. The study group consisted of 358 participants (278 women 80 men). The data were collected using Demographic Information Form, Young Internet Addiction Test Short Form, Procrastination Tendency Scale, Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support, and Anxiety Sensitivity Index-3. Correlational analysis was used to determine the relations among variables. Multiple regression analysis was used to determine whether the independent variables predicted internet addiction. Procrastination ($\beta = .38$), social support ($\beta = -.11$), and anxiety sensitivity ($\beta = .33$) predicted internet addiction at a statistically significant level. It can be inferred considering this finding that, the regression model which involves procrastination, social support, and anxiety sensitivity predicts 31% of internet addiction. Individuals who are lonely have higher levels of internet addiction than those who have a statistically significant relationship, and their perceived social support levels are lower than those who have a statistically significant relationship. Based on the findings some suggestions were made.

Keywords: Anxiety Sensitivity, Internet Addiction, Procrastination, Perceived Social Support

1. Introduction

Internet addiction is a problem that needs to be dealt with, which negatively affects the development of the individual, one's intra-psychic and interpersonal relationships, like many types of addiction. This situation can prepare the ground for a life that is rich in the virtual environment but isolated in the real environment. An isolated life may cause the individual to stay away from social support networks, as well as cause individuals who do not

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receive social support to turn to the internet environment and therefore develop internet addiction. Individuals have started to communicate online with social networks during the pandemic. Similarly, business life and education process continued via the internet. The individual's staying away from social environments may cause a lack of psychological benefits of social relations. This distance can create emotional problems in the individual. The individual spends more time on the internet to deal with all these problems (Şahan & Çapan, 2017). Social support as a universal human being need, can be met over the internet, and it can be resulted internet addiction. Procrastination, which is a behavior that can be seen in many types of addiction, can be exhibited by the individual in social, professional, personal, and relational areas. At this point, the tendency to procrastinate may be a behavior that will emerge because of internet addiction. When the individual exhibits the behavior of procrastination, individuals may prefer to use the internet instead of the behavior she has postponed. In this process, the internet can turn into an addiction and the individual can make the behavior of using the internet a habit instead of every postponed behavior. With the decrease in face-to-face communication in their relationships, there may be changes in the anxiety levels of individuals or their sensitivity to situations that may cause anxiety. The individual may prefer to spend time on the Internet to avoid conditions that will cause anxiety. In such a case, anxiety sensitivity can also be considered as a factor that increases internet addiction. In this context, the need to identify some factors related to internet addiction of the individual arises. Therefore, in this study, it is aimed to examine the relationships between internet addiction and individuals' procrastination tendencies, perceived social support and anxiety sensitivity.

1.1. Internet Addiction

The Internet has become a tool that is the center of attention of many people less than half a century after its invention. Every passing year, the Internet is widely used as a communication and information tool. Until March 2021, 5 billion 168 million people use the internet which corresponds 65.63 of whole world population, and the rate of internet usage in Turkey in 2021 is 82.6% for individuals in the 16-74 age group which is very close to Europe rate, 87.7% (Internet World Stats Usage and Population Statistics, 2021). Although its main purpose is to provide information exchange, the spread of the internet has led to new problem areas such as pathological overuse and internet addiction, which can be considered as a new type of addiction and has led researchers to work on these issues (Kutlu et al., 2016).

The concept of addiction is mostly used as the inability to stop using a substance or control a behavior (Günüç & Kayri, 2010). Internet addiction, 'compulsive internet use,' 'pathological internet use,' and 'internet addictive behavior' interchangeably used for problematic internet use (de Vries et al., 2018). Goldberg (1996) was the first person who created the definition of 'Internet addiction' and tried to explain the diagnostic criteria, and thus entered the literature as the concept of 'internet addiction' (cited in Doğan, 2013). Internet addiction can be defined as excessive use of the Internet and not being able to prevent this desire, feeling the need to spend more time, if no connection to the Internet, extreme tension, nervousness, and restlessness occur and leads to negativities in the individual's work, social and family life (Young, 2004). People with five or more of the following eight criteria defined by Young (1998) can be considered as addicted, and those who have less than five criteria can be considered normal internet users.

1. Excessive engagement with the Internet (thinking about previous online activities or thinking about the next online session)
2. Need to use the internet more and more to feel satisfaction.
3. Unsuccessful attempts to control, diminish, or stop Internet use.
4. Feeling pessimistic, depressed, or restless when trying to reduce or stop Internet use.
5. Staying online longer than intended.
6. Risking or losing a significant relationship, job, educational or career opportunity because of Internet use
7. Lying to family members, therapists, or peers to hide the extent of involvement with the Internet.

8. Using the Internet to escape from problems or alleviate a dysphoric mood (for example, helplessness, guilt, anxiety, depression) (Beard and Wolf, 2001 as cited in Karaca, 2019, p. 10).

The reasons for the purpose of using the internet can be because of psychological and sociological factors. As in substance addictions, the individual's social environment or her/his own curiosity mostly comes to the fore intending to internet addiction (Can, 2007). Meanwhile, the inadequacy of communication within the family (Bayraktutan, 2005) and the need to meet the accompanying social needs are factors in the increase in internet use of young individuals and the transformation of this use into an addiction (Ekşi & Ümmet, 2013). Whang, Lee, and Chang (2003) the loneliness levels of internet addicted individuals were high, and loneliness increased the time spent on the internet. Meanwhile, considering the possible causes of internet addiction, it has been found that individuals use the internet to avoid stress and procrastinate the responsibilities (Gong et al., 2021). The individual may prefer to use the internet as a different job than the job that needs to be done, and this may cause internet addiction. For this reason, it would be useful to examine the role of procrastination in the internet addiction.

1.2. Procrastination

The tendency to procrastinate is defined as the behavior of procrastinating without a valid reason for an important task that an individual has decided to do beforehand (Balkıs, 2006). Procrastination tendency and transforming procrastination into behavior; not wanting to do a task can be expressed as the whole of the stages of producing justified excuses/reasons to psychologically relieve oneself to delay, along with deciding to postpone this task with the condition and belief of doing it at a later time (Knaus, 2000). Procrastination can be viewed as a combination of disbelief in one's ability to perform a task, inability to delay gratification, and attributing one's responsibility to others or blaming someone else for failing to perform actions (Rebetez et al., 2016). In the literature, researchers distinguish procrastination as trait procrastination and state or situational procrastination like academic procrastination. Hence, researchers consider procrastination mostly as a personality trait (Ferrari & Scher, 2000; Milgram et al., 1998; Şirin, 2011), as a tendency to postpone things in general until later (Çakıcı, 2003). Situational procrastination is the procrastination that a person exhibits in only one aspect of her/his daily life (Blunt et al., 1998). Based on the studies on the causes of procrastination, the main reasons for procrastination are the individual's inability to manage time (Balkıs, 2007; Klingsieck, 2013) and anxiety as the first and most important cause (Scher & Osterman, 2002). In this case, anxiety can be evaluated as an active emotional state both as a cause and as a result of procrastination. According to studies based on theoretical foundations, the causes of procrastination are anxiety about failure (Solomon & Rothblum, 1984; Zarick & Stonebraker, 2009), social anxiety (Ferrari, 1992), cognitive test anxiety (Cassady & Johnson, 2002), lack of self-regulation (Klassen et al., 2008), laziness (Senecal et al., 1997), perceiving the task as an imposition (Milgram et al., 1988), learned helplessness (McKean, 1994), low self-esteem (Beswick et al., 1988; Meyer, 2001), low self-confidence (Beswick et al., 1988), self-focused perfectionism (Klingsieck, 2013; Seo, 2008), and external locus of control (Deniz et al., 2009). Along with all these causes, internet addiction has a direct and indirect effect via core self-evaluations on procrastination (Gang et al., 2018), although this result does not explain whether internet addiction is predicted by procrastination or not. In reducing procrastination, perceived social support has an important role (Yang et al., 2021); and social support may also mitigate internet addiction (Wang & Zhang, 2020). For this reason, beyond procrastination, perceived social support can also be important in predicting internet addiction.

1.3. Perceived Social Support

Perceived social support is the individual's belief that he knows the existence of people he can consult when he needs, and that he has interpersonal relationships that satisfy him (Dour et al., 2014; Nur Şahin, 2011). In other words, perceived social support, which is perceived as different from actual or received social support, refers to the individual's personal belief in the existence of social support. It is the sum of the thoughts that the people around her have a secure relationship and that the individual will be supported, and it is the meaning that the individual attributes to her/his social relations (Arıcıoğlu, 2008; Dülger, 2009). While perceived social support

represents the subjective meanings that an individual attributes to the social support from his/her environment, actual or received social support refers to the number of supportive behaviors from individual's social environment that the individual reports (Dour et al., 2014). There are studies examining internet addiction and perceived social support. There is a negative relationship between internet addiction and perceived social support (Esen, & Gündoğdu, 2010; Günüş & Doğan, 2013; Tanrıverdi, 2012; Özcan and Buzlu, 2005). Meanwhile, poor perceived social support predicted internet addiction (Çevik & Yıldız, 2017; Karaer & Akdemir, 2019; Tudorel, & Vintilă, 2018) and poor perceived social support is a risk effect for internet addiction (Chen et al., 1991). The reasons for internet addiction are the obstacles in the social relations of the individual (Inderbitten et al., 1997), the lack of support from the social environment (Papacharissi & Rubin, 2000), and the need to meet their social needs (Ekşi & Ümmet, 2013). Besides, perceived social support mediates anxiety treatment (Dour et al., 2013), while poor perceived social support is associated with anxiety symptoms (Karaer & Akdemir, 2019; Yahyaoğlu, 2019) which can be related to anxiety sensitivity; and anxiety sensitivity may increase internet addiction (Soulioti et al., 2018).

1.4. Anxiety Sensitivity

Anxiety sensitivity is at the core of the 'fear expectation model' in which the motivation to avoid a situation that causes fear in the individual is basically dependent on anxiety sensitivity and anxiety expectation (Mantar et al., 2011; Reiss, 1991). Anxiety sensitivity is characterized as a severe fear that the sensations and symptoms resulting from the individual's anxiety will have physical and/or social consequences that will cause harm (Reiss & McNally, 1985; cited in Elhai et al., 2018). Anxiety sensitivity is a basic fear that exists in the structure of the individual and is constantly recurring (Reiss & McNally, 1985 as cited in Starcevic & Berle, 2006) and intensifies anxiety related symptoms and related to anxiety disorders (Olatunji & Wolitzky-Taylor, 2009). It is 'fear of anxiety' or being afraid of fear as an individual variable with a cognitive structure (Starcevic & Berle 2006). The structure of anxiety sensitivity is based on the various sensations and symptoms associated with anxiety. These symptoms are mainly palpitations, dizziness and sweating and consist of sensations related to autonomic arousal as in panic disorder (Taylor et al., 1991, Reiss, 1991). The individual misinterprets sudden onset, relatively severe, and unexplained symptoms as symptoms of physical origin (Starcevic & Berle 2006). The individual believes that she/he will face a bad situation by making some negative inferences depending on these symptoms. There is some information that an individual's anxiety sensitivity is due to heredity, but it is generally argued that anxiety sensitivity usually originated in childhood as a result of life experiences while interpreting her life experiences in a wrong and negative way (Asmundson et al., 1999). It is different than trait anxiety due to trait anxiety is accepted as a tendency to demonstrate fear to various situations; anxiety sensitivity is a tendency to fear to arouse of body sensations (Stewart & Kushner, 2001). Anxiety sensitivity is related to addictions including alcohol use (Schmidt et al., 2007), problematic internet use (Hashemi et al., 2020, Taş, 2019), and problematic smartphone use (Elhai et al., 2018). The individual may develop internet addiction in order to sling out the effects that increase anxiety and anxiety sensitivity. Individuals with internet addiction may try to escape from reality more than non-addicted individuals (Whang et al., 2003). In this regard, it would be useful to investigate whether anxiety sensitivity predicts internet addiction with other previously stated variables as procrastination, and perceived social support.

1.5. Importance of the Research

The Internet, since it is easily accessible at home, school, workplace, and social environments, it can become an indispensable part of our lives. On the other hand, it can be a problem such as addiction (Yellowlees & Marks, 2007). In most of the research about the Internet, it is acted on that the individual loses his/her own control and experiences problems in social, professional, and academic functioning (Bozkurt et. al, 2016). As in substance addictions, the social environment of the individual or his own curiosity comes to the fore in the tendency to internet addiction (Can, 2007). When examining the literature, procrastination is associated with the internet addiction (Davis et al., 2002; Geng et al., 2018; Thatcher et al., 2007). Perceived social support is associated with internet addiction (Beyrami et al., 2015; Işık & Ergün, 2018). Anxiety sensitivity is associated with Internet addiction (Soulioti et al., 2018). Even though stated variables are related to internet addiction, as far as we reached in the databases, there is no specific research holding procrastination, perceived social support and anxiety

sensitivity together to predict internet addiction. As in other addictions, to cope with internet addiction, the nature of the internet addiction may enrich by this research. Besides it may be possible to bring a different perspective to cope with internet addiction by examining the relationships between procrastination tendency, perceived social support, anxiety sensitivity, and internet addiction.

1.6. Hypotheses

H1. Procrastination, social support, and anxiety sensitivity predict internet addiction.

H2. Internet addiction level varies according to demographic variables of gender, and the presence of romantic relationship.

2. Method

The research was carried out with the descriptive survey method as it examined the relationships between internet addiction, procrastination, perceived social support and anxiety sensitivity. Relational method is frequently used in studies on the relationships between multiple variables related to psychological counseling (Heppner et al., 2008). Internet addiction was the predicted (dependent) variable in the study, and the predictive (independent) variables were procrastination tendency, perceived social support and anxiety sensitivity.

The population of the research consists of all individuals aged 18 and over who use the internet. On the other hand, since online data collection tools were used, the convenient sampling method was used. This sampling method enables easy access to participants when other sampling methods are not applicable.

3. Participants

In the research 358 individuals participated voluntarily and anonymously. 278 (77.7%) were female and 80 (22.3%) were male. The average age of the participants is 42.88. A total of 345 data were selected for the analysis.

3.1. Data Collection Tools

The research was prepared in the form of a Google form and applied in a way that volunteers could fill in an average of 10 minutes.

3.1.1. Personal information form. It included demographic variables of gender, age, educational status, and marital status of the participants.

3.1.2. Young's Internet Addiction Test Short Form (YIAT-SF). The YIAT-SF, which was developed by Young to measure internet addiction. Pawlikowski et al. (2013) decreased the item size to 12 items. It is a five-point Likert scale (1=Never, 5=Very often) (Kutlu et al., 2016). Kutlu et al. (2016) adopted the scale into Turkish. Fit index of confirmatory factor analysis values were $\chi^2=144.93$, $sd=52$, $RMSEA=.072$, $RMR=.70$, $GFI=.93$, $AGFI=.90$, $CFI=.95$, $IFI=.91$. Cronbach alpha was .91, and test re-test reliability in three weeks was .93. In our study, the Cronbach's alpha value was calculated and found to be .84.

3.1.3. Procrastination Tendency Scale. The original form of the scale was developed by Lay (1986) in order to evaluate students' procrastination tendencies in every field in general. The scale is a 5-point Likert-type (1 'Doesn't fit at all,' 5 'Completely fits'). Balkıs (2006) adopted the scale into Turkish. A total of 5 items were removed from

the scale, and the number of items in the scale is 15. According to the factor analysis, the findings have an eigenvalue of 4.80, which constitutes 32.09% of the total variance. A factor (eigenvalue) assumed to be the main factor was found. The internal reliability coefficient was found to be .84 (Balkis, 2006). In our study, the Cronbach's alpha value was calculated and found to be .83.

3.1.4. Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support. The original form of the scale was developed by Zimet et al. (1988). Eker and Arkar (1995) adopted the scale into Turkish. There are 12 items and 3 sub-dimensions in the scale. According to factor analysis, the eigenvalue of 12 items was less than 1 the largest one was included in the relevant 3 factors and the total explained 75% of the variance. The sub-dimensions of the scale are 'family support,' 'friend support' and 'a special person'. Reliability coefficients of the Turkish version of the scale are a special person $\alpha = .92$; family is $\alpha = .85$ and friend is $\alpha = .88$. Overall scale internal consistency score is .89. The scale is a 7-point Likert type scale, and the answers are given between 'definitely yes and absolutely no' (Eker et al., 2001). In our study, the Cronbach's alpha value for overall the scale was calculated and found to be .90.

3.1.5. Anxiety Sensitivity Index-3 (ASI-3). It was developed by Taylor et al. (2007) to measure anxiety sensitivity. The scale consists of physical, cognitive, and social sub-dimensions 18 items in total and all dimensions include six items. The scale has a five-point Likert type measurement, and '0' means too little and '4' means too much. Mantar et al. (2011) adopted the scale into Turkish. In factor analysis it has three factors: physical, cognitive, and social. 3 factor structure explains 61.72% of the total variance. They found the Cronbach's alpha coefficient as .93 (Mantar et al. 2011). In our study, the Cronbach's alpha value was calculated and found to be .93.

3.2. Procedure

Before the data gathering, Sakarya University Rectorate Ethical compliance permission was requested from the Ethics Committee. Ethical permission was obtained with the document numbered E.7805 on 07/09/2020. Later, permissions for the use of scales were obtained via e-mail from the authors. The scales were administered via Google Forms to individuals aged 18 and over, whose personal information is confidential, who voluntarily participated and filled out the informed consent form.

4. Data Analysis

In line with the hypotheses of the research, the data were evaluated using Pearson correlation and multiple regression analysis, t-test and one-way analysis of variance. Relationships between variables were determined using Pearson correlation analysis. After Pearson correlation analysis, whether the independent variables (the ones related to the dependent variable) predicted the dependent variable significantly or not was evaluated using regression analysis. Mahalanobis' distance values were detected to determine whether there were multivariate extremes in the data set, these values were then evaluated on the basis of $p < .001$ significance level, and accordingly it was determined that there were 31 of data that impairs the premises of "normality" and "linearity" in the dataset, so these data were excluded from the dataset. In addition, whether the dependent variable changed according to demographic variables was evaluated with t test, one-way analysis of variance and Welch test. In this context, t-test was used to evaluate whether the levels of internet addiction, procrastination, perceived social support and anxiety sensitivity differ according to gender. One-way analysis of variance was applied to determine whether individuals' internet addiction levels differ significantly according to age and educational status. During this analysis, one-way analysis of variance was used in case of homogeneous variance, and Welch test was applied in case of non-homogeneous variance. Levene's statistics were applied to determine the homogeneity of the variances.

5. Results

The correlations between variables were examined using Pearson correlation analysis and the obtained results are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics and Correlations

Variables	1	2	3	4
Internet addiction	1			
Procrastination	.44**	1		
Social support	-.23**	-.15**	1	
Anxiety sensitivity	.39**	.13*	-.19**	1
$\bar{x}$	24.75	35.77	62.48	24.39
<i>Std. Dev.</i>	6.56	11.20	16.42	16.61

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).*

A positive significant correlation between internet addiction and procrastination ($r = .44$), and anxiety sensitivity ($r = .39$) and a negative correlation between social support ($r = -.23$) at the .001 level as seen in Table 1. Meanwhile, other significant Pearson correlation coefficients were found between the procrastination and social support ($-.15$), and procrastination and anxiety sensitivity ($.13$). Also, there was found social support and anxiety sensitivity ($-.19$). Based on these findings, it was investigated whether internet addiction was statistically significantly predicted by procrastination, social support, and anxiety sensitivity using multiple regression analysis.

The suitability of data for regression analysis was evaluated using Mahalanobis' distance values, kurtosis, skewness values and normal distribution graph. In this respect, firstly Mahalanobis' distance values were detected to determine whether there were multivariate extremes in the data set, these values were then evaluated on the basis of $p < .001$ significance level, and accordingly it was determined that there were 31 of data that impairs the premises of "normality" and "linearity" in the dataset, so these data were excluded from the dataset. Afterwards, indicators of normal distribution (kurtosis, skewness, and normal distribution graph) were analyzed to examine the suitability of dataset for regression analysis. The obtained results were presented in Table 2 and Figure 1.

Table 2: Results about the Assumptions of Normal Distribution and Regression Analysis

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Skewness</i>	<i>Kurtosis</i>	<i>VIF</i>	<i>CI</i>
Internet addiction	.43	-.38		
Procrastination	.54	-.62	1.03	3.68
Social support	-.67	-.05	1.06	6.51
Anxiety sensitivity	.66	-.41	1.5	13.34

Figure 1: Normal Distribution Curve

Table 3: Results of Regression Analysis

Dependent variable	Predictor Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Internet addiction	Constant	16.49	1.74		9.49	.000
	G. Procrastination	.22	.03	.38	8.11	.000
	Social support	-.05	.02	-.11	-2.37	.018
	Anxiety sensitivity	.13	.02	.33	6.90	.000

$F(3,323)= 50.48, p<.0001$

$R= .565; R^2= .313$

As shown in Table 3, procrastination ($\beta= .38$), social support ($\beta= -.11$), and anxiety sensitivity ($\beta= .33$) predicted internet addiction at a statistically significant level as shown in the table. It can be inferred considering this finding that, the regression model which involves procrastination, social support, and anxiety sensitivity predicts 31% of internet addiction.

5.2. Results Related to the presence of romantic relationship

Table 5: The Results of T-test for Presence of Romantic Relationship

	<i>Romantic Relationship Status</i>	Levene's Test				T-Test			
		<i>N</i>	$\bar{X}$	<i>S. D.</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
Internet addiction	Single	172	27,13	7,233	.039	.843	4.034	325	.000
	With a partner	186	23,60	6,917					

Procrastination	Single	172	36,54	11,168	1.444	.230	1.267	325	.206
	With a partner	186	35,32	10,617					
Social support	Single	172	57,02	16,391	3.283	.071	-6.159	325	.000
	With a partner	186	66,97	14,421					
Anxiety sensitivity	Single	172	25,01	15,925	.175	.676	.512	325	.609
	With a partner	186	24,37	16,750					

As indicated in Tables 5 internet addiction and social support levels significantly varied depending on the romantic relationship status of the participants. Regarding internet addiction, the mean scores of single participants ($\bar{x}=27.13$) were statistically and significantly higher than participants with a partner ($\bar{x}=23.60$). Meanwhile, regarding social support, the mean scores of single participants ($\bar{x}=57.02$) were statistically and significantly lower than participants with a partner ($\bar{x}=66.97$). No significant difference was found regarding procrastination and anxiety sensitivity.

6. Discussion

In this study, there is a positive relationship between internet addiction and procrastination and anxiety sensitivity, and a negative significant relationship between internet addiction and perceived social support. In other words, as the procrastination tendency and anxiety sensitivity increase, internet addiction increases; and as perceived social support increases, internet addiction decreases. Besides, internet addiction was predicted by procrastination, social support and anxiety sensitivity as we hypothesized.

According to the findings of our study, individuals with a high procrastination tendency are likely to have more internet addiction and procrastination predicted internet addiction. In literature, procrastination predicts internet addiction better than academic procrastination (Uzun et al. 2004), and those who procrastinate tend to be more vulnerable to internet addiction (Genga et al., 2018). According to the cognitive behavioral approach, the person who shows the behavior of procrastination prefers to do other things instead of starting work (Burka & Yuen, 1983 as cited in Akbay, 2009). The behavioral approach also argues that procrastination is a behavior that provides pleasure to the individual for a short time (Lamba, 1999). In line with these perspectives, participants who have higher procrastination scores in this study may delay the things they should do; instead spend more time to have instant pleasure while being on the internet and this situation may turn into a habit and then an internet addiction. Whatever they do on the internet (social media, online games, web-surfing, or whatever they have fun), the participants of this study may procrastinate the things and prefer instant pleasure instead of doing what they should do. In line with this finding, overcoming procrastination may help coping with internet addiction.

According to our findings, individuals with a lower perceived social support had higher internet addiction scores and perceived social support predicted internet addiction negatively. When individuals experience obstacles in their social relations, they often resolve them through the Internet to maintain their personal relations (Inderbitten et al., 1997; Papacharissi & Rubin, 2000). Hence, the inadequacy in family communication and the need to meet social needs are effective in the increase of internet use and its transformation into an addiction (Bayraktutan, 2005; Ekşi & Ümmet, 2013; Özcan & Buzlu, 2005; Tanrıverdi, 2012). Whang et al. (2003) concluded that internet addicted individuals have high levels of loneliness, and that loneliness increases the time spent on the internet. In other words, inadequate perceived social support can accelerate internet addiction. It may be similar participants in our research. Participants who have lower levels of perceived social support may compensate it via pseudo social relations through social media, if they have problems in their families they may suppress the lack of social support with online games, and such kinds of activities may provoke internet addiction. To cope with internet addiction, social support of individuals may be enhanced. If the individual learns more appropriate social skills,

overcomes social fears she may have more social support, so helping the individuals with lower social support such skills may prevent them the internet addiction.

Our findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between internet addiction and anxiety sensitivity and anxiety sensitivity predicted internet addiction. Anxiety sensitivity has “fear of bodily symptoms”, “fear of losing cognitive control”, and “fear of being aware of anxiety symptoms”. Physically, the individual is afraid of having a heart attack and experiencing shortness of breath (Rodriguez et al., 2004; Watt & Stewart, 2000). In the cognitive dimension of anxiety sensitivity, the individual thinks that she will have difficulty focusing her mind or controlling her thoughts (Taylor et al., 2008). The social dimension of anxiety sensitivity includes fears about being noticed by the society (Taylor, 1995). Similarly, individuals with internet addiction tend to escape from reality more than non-addicts Whang et al. (2003). In our study, individuals with higher anxiety sensitivity may escape from such mental and social difficulties and change his or her focus from reality to virtual universe via internet use to get away from factors that increase anxiety sensitivity. In other words, if people with higher anxiety sensitivity may regulate their anxiety, they may be less likely to develop internet addiction.

In our study, mean scores of single participants regarding internet addiction were statistically and significantly higher than participants with partners. While keeping in mind that single individuals are more prone to internet addiction (Ko et al., 2007; Yen et al., 2007), and they try to eliminate the perception of loneliness through sharing sites and interactive chats, thus reinforcing their addictive behavior with the feeling of relaxation (Tsai & Lin, 2000; Caplan, 2007 cited in Aslan & Yazıcı, 2016). Single participants of our study may feel the same way to keep away feelings of loneliness and have relaxation via internet use. Such an escape via internet may lead to internet addiction. Regarding perceived social support, in our study, single participants' mean scores were statistically and significantly lower than those with one partner. When the perceived social support level is low, the individual feels lonely (Salimi & Bozorgpour, 2012; Suri et al., 2019) and use the internet more (Büyükşahin-Çevik & Yıldız, 2017). Meanwhile, a partner may be perceived the first social support and prevents the individual heavy feelings of loneliness. As a result, single individuals of our participants may have higher internet addiction scores due to the lower perceived social support. In this regard, if the individuals' social skills are improved, they may have more social bonds and it may enhance their social support as a result internet addiction may decrease.

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